

STANDARD OF LIVING AND STATE SOCIAL POLICY

Xodjaniyazov Shohruh Yuldashevich

"Ma'mun University" Faculty of Social and Humanities,
Teacher of the Department of Economics.

Saburov Javohir Kaxramon o'g'li

"Ma'mun University" Faculty of Social and Humanities,
Teacher of the Department of Economics.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11207708>

The standard of living of the population is the level of providing the population with the material and spiritual benefits necessary for living and satisfying their needs with these benefits.

The population's demand for material and spiritual benefits varies and changes rapidly depending on the natural, historical, national and other conditions. Accordingly, the indicators representing the standard of living of the population are also different.

The standard of living of a person is related to the dialectical connection between the level of growing demands and the level of opportunities to satisfy them and its change. In this, the freedom of choice of a person should be increased, that is, he should be able to freely choose what to eat, where, how to live, how to study and learn.

Key words: Population welfare, preferential loans, human freedom, GDP, real income, population needs.

The system of indicators of the standard of living of the population recommended by the UN includes the following groups: 1. Birth and death rates and other demographic indicators. 2. Sanitary and hygienic living conditions. 3. Consumption of food products. 4. Accommodation conditions. 5. Information and culture. 6. Working and employment conditions. 7. Incomes and expenses of the population. 8. Cost of living and consumer prices. 9. Vehicles. 10. Organization of recreation. 11. Social security. 12 Human freedom. In addition to these basic indicators, some more informational indicators are distinguished: GDP per capita, national income per capita, income per capita appropriate consumption volume and others. The set of goods necessary for people's life activities includes such diverse needs as working conditions, education, health care, food and housing quality. The level of satisfaction of people's needs depends on the level of individual and family income of society members. Living standards can be measured at the national level (for the entire population) and at the stratified micro level (for a specific group of the population). The first approach makes it possible to determine the standard of living of the population in different countries according to the gross domestic product per capita and make a comparative analysis. Real income per capita is a generalized and integrated indicator of the standard of living of the population. In the economy, the income in the hands of the population after deducting all mandatory and voluntary payments (taxes, loan money, contributions) from the gross monetary income is also important. Taxes have a strong impact on the amount of income that reaches the hands of the population. In developed countries, wages make up 2/3 of income. The population's demand for material and spiritual benefits varies and changes rapidly depending on natural, historical, national and other conditions.

Accordingly, the indicators representing the standard of living of the population are also different. The standard of living of a person is related to the dialectical connection between

the level of growing demands and the level of opportunities to satisfy them and its change. In this, the freedom of choice of a person should be increased, that is, he should be able to freely choose what to eat, where, how to live, how to study and learn. Therefore, in order for a person's standard of living to increase, he must have the necessary economic resources (opportunities) to expand his freedom of choice, live a long and healthy life, and acquire knowledge. It also includes issues of peace, security, ecology and social justice.

The set of goods necessary for people's life activities includes such diverse needs as working conditions, education, health care, food and housing quality. The level of satisfaction of people's needs depends on the level of individual and family income of society members. The standard of living can be determined at the country level (for a specific group of the population) and at the stratified micro level (for a specific group of the population). The first approach is the standard of living of the population in different countries per capita. Comparison of the dynamics of income distribution by population groups is carried out on the basis of the consumer budget. There are a number of types of consumer budgets: average family budget, high-income budget, minimum income budget, pensioners and other social groups' budget, among them.

The standard of living is inextricably linked with the way of life of people. Lifestyle is a socio-economic category that reflects the type and methods of life activity of people (society, social class, individual) in the national and world community. Lifestyle covers various aspects of human life, namely:

- labor, social forms of its organization;
- forms of life and free time use;
- participation in political and social life-forms of meeting material and spiritual needs;
- norms and rules of people's behavior in everyday life.

As a result of the distribution and redistribution of the gross domestic product, incomes of the population are formed. Population income means the amount of money and in-kind receipts received by them in a certain period of time (for example, in a year)

Regardless of the level of economic development of the states, one of their main tasks is to ensure long-term inclusive development by conducting socio-economic policies aimed at reducing unemployment and improving the well-being of all sections of the population.

In this regard, due to the fact that the measures implemented in different countries and their implementation are different from each other, their effectiveness is the cause of heated debates and discussions among economists, politicians and experts.

It is natural for liberal economists to ask whether financial incentives should be given to reduce poverty and create jobs in a market economy, whether these incentives are inconsistent with the principles of justice, and to what extent and in which sectors and sectors the state should intervene in the economy case

In general, the analysis of the experience of developing foreign countries shows that the targeted financial resources allocated by the state to the needy and needy strata of the population are correctly and fairly directed to ensure employment of the population, increase the standard of living and well-being, and has given its positive results in expanding business opportunities.

According to international experience, it has been observed that these benefits and financial assistance are effective when implemented in parallel with other socio-economic reforms (education, vocational training, economic liberalization).

Each country has its own approach to poverty reduction, and due to the differences in countries' level of development, population outlook, values and traditions, geographical location, the mechanism used in one country can be copied and used in another. application in the state may not be effective.

In particular, developed countries support the population in need mainly through direct financial resources, while in developing countries, the main focus is on training the population in the necessary skills and competences. , is focused on increasing their earning potential and creating conditions for entrepreneurship (production, service provision) by providing them with initial capital.

In particular, in China, the population was lifted out of poverty at the expense of improving the efficiency of land and water resources use. The main focus is on the distribution of state land to families and the introduction of market principles to land relations. As a result, China managed to lift nearly 600 million people out of poverty in the last 30 years.

"Grameyen Bank", established in Bangladesh, served as a catalyst for the comprehensive development of the socio-economic conditions of the poor, who cannot use traditional financial services due to their poverty.

Preferential bank loans were initially allocated in small amounts by forming groups of 4-5 people and providing them with one-week financial training.

In this case, a larger amount of credit was given at the next stage only if all members of the team returned the previous loan on time. As a result, 5% of those participating in the bank's preferential microcredit program had the opportunity to lift their families out of poverty every year.

Such a financing mechanism was created for the very poor population (lacking basic living conditions, housing, clothing), and its use in countries with a relatively high standard of living has not been effective.

Countries such as India and Indonesia, primarily through rural development, including improving access to schools, kindergartens, and medical facilities through infrastructure improvements, and providing financial support to members of the financially disadvantaged, particularly youth and women, to create a new source of income has been able to lift millions of people out of poverty by providing methods.

The history of the creation and development of the system of providing financial assistance to the needy and needy segments of the population of Uzbekistan. Having studied the international experience and based on the country's specific characteristics, in recent years, financial support to the needy and needy segments of the population has been introduced in Uzbekistan. Great attention is being paid to improving their well-being through comprehensive measures such as assistance, vocational training, and involvement in entrepreneurship.

In the recent past, the recognition of the existence of poverty for the first time in the country was one of the important steps in providing targeted assistance to this category of population, ensuring their employment, and improving their living conditions.

In this case, work on ensuring the employment of the poor strata of the population is carried out taking into account the specific characteristics and socio-economic situation of each region, district, village and neighborhood of the country.

For this purpose, to determine the "growth points" (directions of specialization) of each neighborhood, to study "household-by-house" the level of land use of households in the neighborhoods, the sources of income of families, and the directions of interest in engaging in profitable work. A "neighborhood" work system was introduced in the regions, which envisages attracting them to entrepreneurship.

Starting from 2018, by attracting the population to entrepreneurship in the regions and thereby creating new jobs, supporting employment, providing practical assistance to citizens who want to earn income with their own labor, and by rationally using labor resources, every family "Every family is an entrepreneur" program was introduced in order to create conditions for them to engage in entrepreneurship and have a stable source of income.

In 2018-2021, preferential loans in the amount of 23.7 trillion soums were allocated to nearly one million families within the framework of family business programs (on average per family If there are 4-5 people, these preferential loans amount to 4-5 million. in the first 11 months of 2021, over 8.0 trillion soums of preferential loans were allocated to 332,600 people and business entities within the framework of the "Every family is an entrepreneur" program.

Also, taking into account the growing demand for qualified labor resources in the country and the fact that the majority of the working-age population is made up of young people, special attention is paid to ensuring their employment by providing them with the necessary qualifications for modern professions, retraining, and comprehensive support for entrepreneurial ideas. attention is being paid.

In 2018-2021, within the framework of the "Youth is our future" program and other programs for the development of family entrepreneurship, preferential loans in the amount of 1.8 trillion soums were allocated to 25 thousand young people as initial capital for the implementation of their business projects and the creation of sources of income.

At the same time, in recent years, a comprehensive approach has been implemented in order to increase the role of women in the economy and ensure their employment. It should be noted that, historically, women in the regions of Central Asia have been mainly busy with child care, which has been one of the main obstacles to their fulfilling work.

In this regard, first of all, by increasing the coverage of pre-school education in the regions, conditions are being created for women to work fully.

Also, in ensuring women's employment, special attention is paid to training them in modern professions such as information technology and forming entrepreneurship skills, not limited to traditional professions such as tailoring and cooking. In particular, as of November 1, 2021, 973.6 billion soums will be given to 65.2 thousand women included in the "Women's Register", 1.3 trillion soums will be allocated to 56.6 thousand young people included in the "Youth Register", Preferential loans in the amount of 94.4 billion soums were directed to 5,700 citizens included in the "Iron Register". For information: at the end of 2020, the unemployment rate increased from 9% to 10.5% at the end of 2019, and as of October 1, 2021, it decreased to 9.4%.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fuqarolik kodeksi. O'zbekiston Respublikasining 21.12.1995 y. 163-I-son va 29.08.1996 y. 256-I-son Qonunlari bilan tasdiqlangan.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 7-fevraldagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida" gi PF-4947-sonli Farmoni
3. Yuldashevich, X. S., & Abdullayevich, S. O. (2023). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING AHOLI TUMUSH FARAVONLIGIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 22(10), 34-36.
4. Xodjaniyazov , S. ., & Atayev , J. (2024). THEORETICAL METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPROVING THE WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITIZATION OF THE ECONOMY . Наука и инновация, 2(13), 66–68.

